
BLOGPOST 4

One Year In

PRESERVE Consortium in Malaga

The PRESERVE consortium held its 3rd workshop and General Assembly in Málaga on September 24-25th. Organized by [CIFAL Málaga](#), the meeting took place at the historic Hospital Noble, a national landmark in the city center. The venue is located near the Parque de Málaga, the main port and beaches, with a view of the Gibralfaro Castle. Given the recent cold spell across much of Europe, the participants particularly enjoyed the warm and sunny weather.

After a warm welcome from the hosting organization, the coordinator, [Eduardo Villamor Medina](#), reminded us that this General Assembly also marked the project's first anniversary. Happy birthday to PRESERVE! In this blog post, we highlight some of the main accomplishments from this first year.

The innovative paradigm of the PRESERVE project is to consider drone threats as planned actions that can be detected, intercepted, and neutralised through a combination of online intelligence gathering, multi-sensor fusion, behaviour analysis, and adaptive mitigation. The project addresses a particularly relevant challenge in light of recent incursions by drones at several European commercial and military airports, which have caused flight disruptions.

The PRESERVE platform incorporates multi-drone detection via the fusion of radar, RF, optical and acoustic sensors to track and analyze the individual drones and the swarm behaviour for possible threatening activities as well as continuous online intelligence monitoring of the surface web and dark web, monitoring sources such as social media platforms, online marketplaces, incident reports, planned events, and even weather predictions. The collected data is then analysed using state-of-the-art AI-based multilingual language, speech, and image processing components to effectively monitor text, audio, video, and image data. All of the gathered information is then processed by the Risk assessment module which aims to determine the risk of a terrorist attack aiding operators to take decisions on follow-up actions taking into account the context of the incident as well as local and national regulations.

The use of AI-based algorithms makes it crucial to ensure fairness, prevent bias, and protect sensitive data. PRESERVE gives high priority to privacy and ethical considerations, integrating them from the earliest stages of proto-type and demonstrator design. This "ethics by design" approach ensures proactive compliance with evolving EU and national regulatory requirements, maintaining a balance between security and privacy.

Overall, the project is progressing according to plan, having successfully completed all 7 deliverables and 3 milestones scheduled for the first year. Project oversight includes continuous risk monitoring, periodic updates of the data catalog, and regular technical meetings involving the Users and Ethics teams.

One of the main activities of this first project phase was the definition of User Requirements and their mapping to the technical specifications of the PRESERVE prototype. This was accomplished in an iterative fashion during 2 user workshops (+ 13 technical meetings). With these steps now complete, the project has entered its prototyping phase, which will continue over the next six months and culminate at the next consortium meeting in spring 2026.

The Málaga meeting was packed with updates from all partners and engaging discussions with end-users. On the second day, a visual analytics working session was held, where the functionalities of the dashboard were presented to representatives of the Spanish National Police and the Moldovan Ministry of Internal Affairs. Their feedback was invaluable for shaping the next iteration of the system. The project has also actively pursued collaborations with other EU projects and with international standards and regulatory organizations, including HRSN, Europol, JRC, ISF COURAGEOUS-2, as well as related project clusters such as AI4SafeEurope and Secure Worship & Public Spaces. Looking ahead, the next steps will focus on further development of the prototype and on testing different sensors in realistic environments using representative drones, in close collaboration with the users. Engagement with Stakeholders and the External Advisory Board will also play a central role in guiding the project's next phases.

If you are interested in joining our stakeholder group, please sign up at <https://preserve-he.eu/stakeholders-groups/>

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